

Disaster Journalism Guide

“Protecting Life Safety and Human Dignity is Essential”

Reporting for disaster risk management should be an inherent part of journalism curriculum and media discourse. Information reduces risk and journalism training and communication strategies should always be geared towards improving the ability of media to communicate with a purpose.

In this regard, Journal of Media Literacy Studies, under the coordination of Assoc. Dr. Hediyeullah Aydeniz as Editor-in-Chief and under the leadership of the Editorial Board, prepared the Disaster Journalism Guide, which focuses on “life safety and human dignity”, with the evaluation and contribution of names from academia, civil society and the media coming together to discuss and review the state of the art in disaster reporting.

In the preparation of this Guide, the journalism practices of the media between February 6 and February 20 were taken into account in the reporting of the disaster caused by two devastating earthquakes that occurred one after the other in Turkey on February 6, 2023. The first version of the text was published on February 8, 2023, the third day of the earthquake, with the title “[Mandatory Reminders to Media Professionals: ‘Protecting Life Safety and Human Dignity is First and Foremost’](#)”. In the process after the publication of the text, a draft text focusing on solution proposals within the framework of “disaster reporting” was prepared based on the follow-up of earthquake news and the problems identified. The opinions and suggestions of students, academics and media sector employees who attended the consultation meeting held on February 14, 2023 with the title of “[Disaster Journalism: We are Gathering for a Humane Journalism Respecting Human Dignity](#)” were received. The resulting draft text was presented for the evaluation of academics from different disciplines, both orally and in writing, and was made better by taking their opinions. In addition, within the scope of Müktesebat Toplantıları (the Acquis Meetings), where we discussed and shared Turkey’s academic and intellectual knowledge, the subject was also discussed in the session titled “[Infodemic and Disaster: How Can Misinformation Be Prevented?](#)” by our journal editorial board member Assoc. Dr. F. Bilge Şenyüz.

In the evaluation of the two-week earthquake reporting practices of the media in Turkey, it was also utilized from the experiences of professional principles that the media and communication sector has revealed so far. The Disaster Journalism Guide consists of 43 items in total, which was prepared with a collective effort and focused on the principle of “protecting life safety and human dignity”, included “Infodemic and Journalism”, “Protecting Life Safety”, “Humanitarian Journalism Protecting Human Dignity”, “Strengthening Social Resilience” and Empowering Journalists and Journalism”.

The Disaster Journalism Guide is also pertinent for digital news producers, publishers and every person and institution that takes part in social media platforms regardless of the number of followers where infodemic is more effective.

We would like to thank the contributing students, members of civil society, academia, the media, and all journalists who show sensitivity on these issues, with the hope that it will be useful.

Editorial Board

*The list of contributors is available at the following [link](#).

Infodemic and Disaster Journalism

- *In disasters, the spread of misinformation threatens life safety.*
 - *One of the ways to reduce the risk of life safety depends on accurate and up-to-date news.*
 - *The most important source of accurate and up-to-date news is the institutionalized media.*
1. Infodemic, which means the rapid and wide spread of true, false, fake and distorted information at the same time, indistinguishable from each other, is as risky for human life as natural disasters such as Covid and earthquake and terrorist attacks, delaying disaster response, reducing social resistance, and it is a public health problem that makes it difficult to solve the problems caused by the disaster.
 2. In disaster periods when the inability to distinguish between true, false, fake or distorted information endanger the safety of life or even cost human life; one of the possibilities of not getting caught in the infodemic, and overcoming the infodemic is media literacy, while the most basic resistance point is “up-to-date and accurate news”. Therefore, the existence of a transparent, accountable, strong and institutionalized media is vitally important.
 3. Access to accurate and up-to-date news is an important need, a fundamental right. Media is the main way to access accurate and up-to-date news. For this reason, freedom of the press/media, which is considered within the scope of “freedom of expression and dissemination of thought”, is one of the fundamental rights guaranteed by the constitution.
 4. Journalism is a public service and is based on the public interest. The rights of the journalist also form the basis of the public’s right to know, access to information and freedom of expression.
 5. By observing the principles of honesty and accuracy, the reporter reports the event in the simplest and most realistic way in natural disasters and extraordinary situations such as floods, earthquakes and wars, with the responsibility of witnessing history.

Protecting Life Safety

- *Accurate and up-to-date news can save lives in the disaster area.*
 - *Fake and false news can even lead to death.*
 - *Broadcasting that puts life at risk should be avoided.*
 - *All kinds of attitudes and behaviors that will weaken search and rescue efforts should be avoided.*
6. Accurate and up-to-date information can save lives in the disaster area and during the search and rescue process, on the other hand, fake and false information can even lead to the death of innocent people, in addition to other kinds of damages.
 7. Reporters working in the disaster area should refrain from all kinds of attitudes and behaviors that may hinder the search and rescue efforts. Photography, drone (UAV) and camera shots should be done in a way that does not endanger the life safety of those under the debris and search and rescue teams.
 8. The newsgathering process (especially announcements and interviews) should be done with a sensitivity that ensures maximum safety and facilitates the work of search and rescue teams.

For example, microphones should not be hand to people under the wreckage, and the race to view the moment of being pulled out of the wreckage should be avoided as it may endanger the life safety of the victims.

9. Broadcasting that puts life at risk, such as trying to show the practices of search and rescue teams to detect people under the rubble, should be avoided in live broadcasts.
10. Reporters should avoid entering the earthquake debris in order not to risk the life safety of those waiting to be rescued, search and rescue personnel, and themselves, while the search and rescue efforts continue in the wreckage.
11. During the hustle and bustle of the news gathering process, it is necessary to act with the awareness that the sound and light of photographic apparatus and cameras may adversely affect the health and psychological state of the victims. In particular, maximum sensitivity should be shown in taking pictures and reporting of persons with disabilities and special needs.

Journalism that Protects Human Dignity

- *Observing human dignity is essential and a priority.*
 - *The rights of the disaster victims cannot be violated for the sake of reporting.*
 - *The use of images that will hurt the victims should be avoided.*
12. A publishing approach to protect the personal rights of disaster victims and their relatives should be carefully observed and implemented despite all possible difficulties.
 13. Particular attention should be paid to the issue of children's rights and privacy, which is preached by basic human values and agreed upon by international conventions. Maximum sensitivity should be displayed to the reporting of families with Down syndrome and children with special needs. Considering the nature of the digital media to transform into a permanent memory accessible to everyone, it is an obvious requirement of humanitarian journalism to avoid detailed descriptions of children's images and personal information.
 14. It should not be forgotten that the main thing in journalism is to "protect human dignity". Protecting the dignity of disaster victims is a requirement of humanitarian journalism. For this reason, it should be avoided to shoot and publish all the details of the people trapped under rubble and the moments of their being pulled out of the wreckage.
 15. Microphones should not be handed to the victims and/or their relatives without their permission and should not be broadcast live. People waiting in line for help should not be screened in close-up, and people's sense of "embarrassment" should be respected.
 16. In line with the most basic human and professional values, the suffering of people who are broadcasted or interviewed should be approached with respect and care, and they should be allowed to express themselves. Questions that force or manipulate interviewees to express a specific answer should be avoided.
 17. It should be avoided that survivors are made the material of conflicts of interest for any reason, especially polarization, and turning them into news exploitation. In this context, it is a requirement of humanitarian journalism to report disaster survivors with only name and age information, without using phrases that reflect a discriminatory, objectifying and marginalizing language towards the elderly and refugees (e.g. "a Syrian was saved, a migrant was pulled out, even at the age of 80", etc.).

18. It is both a fundamental right and a requirement of humanitarian journalism to allow refugees and other disadvantaged groups, who have been targeted by racism and hate speech, especially through social media, to express themselves in the media.
19. Taking into account consent, privacy and psychological factors of victims and earthquake environment shooting, announcements and interviews are also indispensable for humanitarian journalism.
20. The main feature and importance of the journalism profession is its social quality and being a public service. For this reason, the news should respect personal rights and private life; nationality, race, gender, ethnic origin, religion, language, class discrimination should not be allowed.
21. Any kind of broadcasting aimed at turning the disaster into a commercial “opportunity” for the sake of ratings should be avoided.
22. Journalists should not be content with only bringing certain parts of the disaster area, selected debris and images to the screen or bring them to the agenda, but should be sensitive about reflecting the integrity of the event.

Strengthening Social Resistance

Accurate and up-to-date news is also a great need for social resistance.

Putting the sensation into circulation by reporting is a threat to social peace.

It is out of question to discriminate between disaster victims.

23. Verified up-to-date news is vitally important both for the safety of the victims in terms of meeting their needs, and social solidarity and resilience.
24. While reporting the facts in their simplest form with the responsibility of witnessing history, rumors that may increase social tension, cause social ruptures or conflicts should not be respected, and any sensation should not be reported without being verified from at least two different sources.
25. Based on the principle of “the identity of the victims is not asked”, journalists cannot discriminate among the victims. Publishing/broadcasting that marginalizes, fosters hatred and tension, and fuels hostility and conflict should be avoided.
26. Journalists should not make the cultural values, beliefs or disbelief of the victims the subject of attack, belittle or mock them. All expressions and attitudes within the scope of hate speech should be avoided.
27. Journalists should not make provocative and incitement to violence broadcasting in a way that would risk life safety and harm social cohesion with reference to individual theft, looting or conflicts in the disaster area.
28. Dramatic elements such as background music should not be used in the news in order to affect the audience emotionally. Current/relevant image (video, photo) should be used in the news; It should be avoided to include outdated images, animation, panic, agitation and shock.
29. It is a requirement of human journalism to observe the principles of balance, understanding, constructive approach, respect for exceptional values and human dignity, rather than elements of sensation, panic, agitation and shock in news production processes.

30. Positive journalism as well as negative journalism can have a negative impact on human psychology in the disaster process. Enthusiastic expression, the use of words that will cause an explosion of emotions, and such a style should be avoided. In conveying a positive or negative event or emotional state, a balanced journalism based on appropriate concepts and qualifications should be emphasized by remaining as rational as possible.
31. While describing the rescue from the debris, the reporters should stay away from the enthusiasm and joy that will harm the mourning of thousands of people who have passed away. A balanced news language should be used, taking into account the tone of voice, selected word and expression patterns, and loss and recovery situations.
32. Allowing experts from the fields of health, social sciences and humanities (psychiatry, public health, philosophy, psychology, sociology, theology) to take part in the media, as well as geoscientists, will facilitate the understanding and management of the disaster, which is a multidimensional social destruction.
33. The news from the disaster areas where refugees and immigrants live intensely show that the negative perception of the society towards these vulnerable groups is not limited to the level of discourse and perception. For this reason, using a news language that is marginalizing, discriminatory and criminalizing especially towards refugees and immigrants, harming social peace and resistance, and presentation forms that will normalize violence and illegal actions should be avoided.

Empowering Journalists and Journalism

- *For accurate and reliable news, the reporter must first be strong and secure.*
 - *The personal rights of journalists should be improved for quality journalism.*
 - *Journalists are primarily responsible to the public and the facts.*
 - *For better quality news, job rotation should be applied in disaster areas.*
 - *Fact-Checking and Infodemic Editorship should be established in the news media organizations*
34. Job security and personal rights of journalists, who are made responsible to the public and the truth before public authorities and employers in the declarations of professional organizations, should be improved.
 35. Priority should be given to the assignment of media professionals who have received disaster and guidance training, have strong psychological strength, and are experienced in disaster reporting.
 36. Considering the weight of working in the disaster area, it should be ensured that the journalists are assigned for short periods (maximum one week) with team rotations and receive psychosocial support once returned from duty.
 37. Disaster management officials should support the working conditions of journalists working in the field, especially technical support, and regularly share up-to-date data with media professionals.
 38. Journalists should develop and use interactive maps, infographics or new narrative/story-telling formats that will allow audiences to better understand the extent and impact of the disaster.
 39. All kinds of visual materials in the media at the time of the disaster should be interpreted by the experts in the field. Fault lines, ground maps, satellite images, which were frequently used in this period, should be interpreted by real experts and scientists in a way that the public can understand.

40. The most important stakeholder of risk and crisis communication, which are the two basic elements of disaster planning and management, is the media and news industry. In this context, strengthening “science and technology journalism” and “urbanization and urban journalism” will make a serious contribution to the socialization of scientific knowledge produced by multiple disciplines related to disaster and disaster management, to the formation of disaster awareness and to the emergence of a proactive social resistance that will minimize the damages.
41. An honest, transparent, responsible, fair and accountable media structure will also provide humanitarian journalism that protects the life safety and human dignity of disaster victims. For this, the media sector (traditional and digital) is obliged to deliver accurate and up-to-date news to the public without being an extension of the advertising and organizational communication departments of the communication sector (public relations, corporate communication, political communication, advertising, etc.).
42. It is expected that the media sector will develop a more effective and functional relationship with national and international fact-checking organizations, both in terms of combating the infodemic and quality journalism. For this purpose, associations of media and communication sector should assume a more active role.
43. In this process, where our information ecosystem is facing a structural problem expressed with the concepts of information crisis, information disorder and infodemic, it has become a necessity to establish a “Fact-Checking and Infodemic Editorial” in all media organizations for a strong and institutionalized media and reliable quality journalism.